
Research

The Use of Aloe Vera As Medicinal Plants and Cultural Plants in the Community from a Health and Culture Perspective

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Abstract: The aloe vera is a medicinal plant that is widely used by the public and has enormous benefits for society. The aloe vera plant has very strong cultural roots in the cultural narrative of society. Of course, this aspect is very important from the perspective of people's culture regarding the aloe vera plant and also in terms of its benefits for health and other aspects. This question relates to the use of the medicinal plant aloe vera as a medicinal plant and also as a cultural medicinal plant in society. The method used is to use the literature review method and existing literature sources. The results of the research show that the use of the medicinal plant aloe vera is culturally rooted in society, making the medicinal plant aloe vera a favourite medicinal plant in people's lives. The cultural roots of the use of the aloe vera are reflected in folklore related to the aloe vera, as a category that shows the closeness and importance of the aloe vera in the crocodile values of a society. These cultural aspects can provide an illustration of how deeply rooted the use of cultural language is in the dimensions of society, which has many benefits and properties for health and beauty.

Keywords: aloe vera, health, culture, society, and medicine

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Introduction

The medicinal plant aloe vera has a very big role in making it a medicinal plant, which has many benefits from various aspects that are also related to improving the community's economy by empowering the community's economy from various existing aspects. In accordance with various conditions resulting from the community's use of the medicinal plant aloe vera. In accordance with the conditions expected from various aspects of health in society, which are provided by adding financial aspects to existing medicinal plants by utilizing their economic aspects, the many benefits obtained from the use of medicinal plants that are used to provide very significant benefits from the expected conditions from various aspects that make changes to the aspects of the benefits that medicinal plants bring, which have made

various aspects of existing medicinal plants with such great beneficial power, the community also responded quite well regarding various aspects of the aloe vera plant in society, which is an inseparable part of the internal medicine of our society. This cultural aloe plant has many uses and benefits that can be carried out to achieve health and beauty.

Traditional medicine is an existing part of society that exists as traditional medicine (1). The aloe vera is a plant that is very well known in Indonesia and is widely used by the Indonesian people for the benefits provided by the plant. For the explanation that we want to give, it turns out that aloe vera is a plant that is widely used in countries in the world, among those that use aloe vera a lot are countries in America such as Congo and China, so it is only natural that aloe vera is known as a miracle plant, and in Indonesia itself, this plant was already known and was introduced in the 17th century (2). From the results of existing research, it is said that the aloe vera plant is an antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antifungal, and cell regeneration plant (2). And apart from that, aloe vera is widely used as a herbal medicine or as a traditional medicine (1), while its function is to control blood pressure and also as an immune medicine against cancer, as well as lowering blood sugar levels (2). For the beauty aspect, it is widely used as a shampoo, apart from being a medicinal plant, as explained above (3), which is efficacious in treating disease (4). For treatment outside the body, aloe vera has a function to heal wounds (5) and also to care for the skin, head, and hair (6). And also, the aloe vera plant is also a medicinal plant, which functions as a promotion for medicinal plants (7).

According to Astuti et al. (2022), this cultural aloe plant is a traditional medicine for healing wounds (8). The aloe vera is a plant that is easy to grow quickly and also easy to cultivate (9). Aloe vera functions as anti-fungal, anti-inflammatory, and anti-bacterial (9). And also the aloe vera, which is used to conduct training on the use of the aloe vera plant (10). With the development of technology and science, the use of aloe vera is not only as an ornamental plant or as medicine but also in the cosmetics industry (11). The aloe vera is a plant that grows easily and quickly, so that in empty yards and also in pots, aloe vera plants can be used (12). Processing aloe vera actually provides income for the community to increase their income (13). The aloe vera plant is used to retain moisture and also prevent ulcers (7). One of the benefits of aloe vera is that it is an antioxidant (14). Aloe vera has many functions as an ingredient for beauty and also as an ingredient for cleaning the face from acne (13). This plant grows widely in Indonesia and is used as a medicinal plant (15).

The medicinal plant Aloe vera is a medicinal plant that has been known for thousands of years and has the function of healing wounds. There are many ingredients in this medicinal plant (16). The aloe vera is a plant that has many benefits. One of the benefits is that it is a basic ingredient in medicine, health drinks, and food ingredients and is very suitable for people on a diet (17). It is said that aloe vera can be combined with various others (18). It turns out that Egyptian queens Cleopatra, Alexander the Great, and Christopher Columbus have used aloe vera in the past. Of course, it was used for beauty purposes and also as medicine for soldiers' wounds. And it also turns out that the first literature about aloe vera existed in 1655 AD, which was translated by John Goodyew into a medical treatise (19). For this reason, this study is interesting to examine regarding the uses of aloe vera as seen from the dimensions of health and culture, which of course reflect the health aspects and also the cultural aspects surrounding aloe vera.

Method

The method used is a qualitative method of conducting a literature review related to the article. By collecting reading materials obtained from existing literature reviews and using them as an analysis of the existing bibliography. This means that data collection is carried out by collecting library data (20). Researchers deal directly with texts (20), library data is a golden addition to library data, which is very good for study (20). The data collection process is carried out by

searching for data in the literature, and from this method, data and problems can be obtained from literature data research (21). From the literature study carried out, the latest reading results and journals were obtained (21). Obtain a lot of reading material from literature studies obtained from the process of searching for literature data (22). A literature review aims to obtain scientific information that can be obtained inductively (22).

Results and Discussion

To discuss the study and uses of aloe vera, looking at the health and cultural aspects. So it is illustrated by the literature and related studies, which are discussed in the summary below. According to the article presented, aloe vera is an herbal product that is useful as a complementary medicine (23). And if you look at it, treatment with aloe vera is a very good treatment and is also a treatment that is based on the traditions that exist in society. As stated in research conducted by Muthu et al. (2006), traditional knowledge was introduced by traditional healers, and the existence of these healers must be maintained in order to preserve traditional medicine (24). This means that aloe vera is a herbal plant that has been used for thousands of years, is used for treatment, and is also used for skin care using a combination of existing herbal plants (25). The aloe vera herbal plant is a product of local wisdom, which is an adapted environmental aspect of the herbal plant (26). Ground aloe vera is used in industry and has greater benefits than the aloe vera plant in the cosmetics and pharmaceutical industries (27). The aloe vera is a plant that has many benefits, is a herbal plant that is beneficial for the health of the body, and is also a plant that comes from cultural plants from deep-rooted cultures. This has been known for a long time, has become part of the practices carried out by the community, and has become a daily habit in processing these herbal plants.

And from the literature presented above, it can be ascertained that the aloe vera plant has high value. The existing literature provides guidance on the importance of the aloe vera medicinal plant, which has very important benefits from the various benefits of the aloe vera medicinal plant. Which provides very good benefits, from medicinal plants which bring very good and important benefits with existing aspects of medicinal plants with various functions from medicinal plants from various medicinal plants which provide good conditions from aloe vera, which is so popular among medicinal plants. It turns out that the aloe vera plant also has great benefits, apart from being medicinal, as well as being a beauty ingredient. This means that aloe vera has benefits for beauty as part of aloe vera, which has benefits for aloe vera as a beauty ingredient from the aloe vera plant.

Aloe vera has components that are very concentrated from the elements contained in medicinal plants, which are so important from the elements carried that always get various elements that are very good in accordance with the expectations of the elements from herbal medicinal plants from the aloe. Historically, it is in accordance with expectations that the aloe vera plant provides benefits for, and its roots are very strong in various important conditions, namely from a long history of history that is in accordance with existing traditions that are so long in the process. The aloe vera plant is known as a traditional plant, which is included in the realm of traditional medicine or ethnomedicine studies (1).

The aloe vera is a natural food and medicine and is used as a food ingredient in the health industry (28). How can aloe vera leaves be used as an ingredient combined with other ingredients (29). The aloe vera is a plant that is widely used in society and apparently has properties as a medicinal plant. It turns out that the aloe vera medicinal plant has quite strong cultural roots and has a legend among the Kedang people in East Nusa Tenggara. The cultural tongue itself is the original tongue of Father Naran. Folklore says that Father Naran had a skin disease that would not heal, and his skin was full of ulcers because this made him lose his existence. He then vowed to move to the sea and change into a

crocodile, while his tongue was left to stay on land and then turned into a tongue plant. Which turns out to have enormous benefits for society. Which is also Bapa Naran (father of sharks), and Are' Naran is a lineage of Uyolewun descendants who are said to be the ancestors of the Kedang people (30).

Which then also brought aloe vera to become a favorite stand in the city of Pontianak (31). It can be said that it turns out that aloe vera as a medicinal plant has such a strong cultural aspect that it has become an inseparable part of society's culture. From the folklore presented, the answer is that the aloe vera plant has great benefits for the community and provides for the importance of this medicinal plant in that community. And the literature indicates that the aloe vera plant is indeed a plant that has been widely studied as a medicinal plant because of the properties that the aloe vera medicinal plant has.

The medicinal plant aloe vera is a medicinal plant, which is a very important part in bringing about the development of medicinal plants, which are very important in existing medicine in accordance with the very important expectations for medicinal plants. It is hoped that medicinal plants will become a very important part of maintaining health and bringing problems from existing medicinal plants in line with the expectations and desires of existing medicinal plants. From the explanation of the literature presented, a conclusion can be drawn and provides insight from the existing presentation that the traditional medicinal plant of aloe vera has become an inseparable part of the nation's culture, which can be seen from the legends in the nation's culture found in society. Of course, this shows that great cultural value has been integrated into the aloe vera medicinal plant, so that it has become a very strong cultural value in society.

Apart from that, the use of the aloe vera in everyday life is also as a medicinal plant, which has many benefits felt by the community, and also as a beauty aid for the aloe vera plant. And also from the research carried out, which was published in scientific journals, it shows that there are many benefits obtained from the aloe vera plant, and the beneficial aspects as stated in the literature stated above can be used. Apart from that, the most important thing is that cultural roots and values have become a core part of the use of the aloe vera in the daily life of our society.

From the discussion above, it is clear that the uses and benefits of aloe vera are seen in both health aspects and cultural aspects of society. Moreover, it tells of folklore related to aloe vera itself, which of course will provide an important picture regarding aloe vera in a cultural and health dimension for the community. And the health aspect is also related to things that are now very popular with the public, namely those related to the beauty aspect. The beauty aspect is highly desired by women who want to be beautiful, and by using aloe vera, the benefits of using aloe vera can be felt.

Conclusion

From the conclusion obtained, the aloe vera plant is a traditional plant that has a very important influence on health, can provide health benefits, has quite good cultural roots, and has a good history. And also culturally, it turns out that there are ethnic groups that have strong cultural strengths in understanding the aloe vera plant and that it has good benefits. Aloe vera has various powers that bring health, which provide benefits to society and health for the aloe vera plant. Aloe vera has health benefits, is an important part of various health processes, and has quite a big influence on building society, which leads to public health. Culturally, it has an influence and has a very important culture for the community, which can be seen from the use of aloe vera, which is an inseparable part of the existing community culture. Which of course also brings benefits to society, and also the culture that exists in society, which of course also provides enormous benefits to society compared to using aloe vera as medicine. As part of the medicinal plants that bring health, they provide very important benefits to society. Health is a very important part of society, which can give people the health they have and provide existing benefits.

Health is an important thing and an important part of various existing conditions, according to aspects that can provide health benefits that lead to existing health. Health is an important part of various aspects of life that is expected from various benefits and in various aspects of the benefits contained in the aloe vera medicinal plant. The aloe vera provides health aspects that are optimized in health according to the needs required from the properties of aloe vera, which brings various aspects of health benefits provided from the aspect of awareness of optimization rather than public health. Health is categorized as very important and must be prioritized in accordance with the needs of the community, which leads to people being healthy both physically and mentally.

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